

Towards an international research software conference (version 4)

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1. Introduction

In 2024, ReSA engaged with key stakeholders in order to identify and recommend one or more community-supported routes for convening the first-ever international research software conference, in 2025 or 2026 (and ideally annually thereafter). This report summarises the findings of this scoping activity and recommends two paths forward around three potential event options, which are:

1. Proceed with a sequential approach to creating three events, beginning with option B (workshops at existing events) in 2025, to build momentum towards all three options taking place in 2026.
2. Form committees led by ReSA to begin development of all three options in early 2025, to enable their convening in 2026.
 - a. Option A: Hybrid annual event
 - b. Option B: Sessions/workshops at multiple existing events

c. Option C: Champions event

The differing community focus of the three different options was seen as particularly important, with these **aims** varying from primarily **deepening engagement with existing stakeholders** (option A), to **broadening stakeholder engagement to overlapping/new communities** (option B), to **supporting future community leaders** (option C). Additionally, this consultation has enabled the community to identify additional needs in terms of community development, which extend beyond annual events to ongoing opportunities throughout the year. It is important to ensure that from the start, event planning includes principles to support both diversity, equity and inclusion; and environment sustainability.

ReSA aims to take the lead in organising these new events. As the sole international organisation facilitating collaboration across the entire research software community (with other groups focusing on specific areas), ReSA has the ability to manage this effectively. However, the coordination and convening of an event will ultimately be dependent on securing funding (which is outside of the scope of this grant) for this event by the organisations who will lead this event. Whilst this report is the final deliverable for ReSA's [grant](#) supporting this work, the community discussions leading to this report have identified stakeholders interested in continuing this work.

2. Background

This activity began by contacting relevant events (with a regional or thematic international focus) to gain their insights on opportunities, including leveraging of their existing community engagement. This resulted in an options paper, [Towards an international research software conference \(version 1\)](#) in July 2024, which includes sections on possible aims, leadership, and business models. This paper was then used as the basis for discussion with a total of 29 people from a range of existing events and invited organisations during three online meetings. [Towards an international research software conference \(version 1\)](#) also lists the organisations that were engaged at each stage, and considers issues related to the conference aim, leadership, business model, structure, and timing.

The inputs from these meetings were then synthesised to create a [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#), for wider discussion that took place in November 2024. ReSA led this community consultation to gain feedback and identify stakeholders who would be interested in shepherding the development of at least one of the three conference options proposed. As part of this public consultation, ReSA invited community members to engage through the following avenues:

- Respond to a [survey](#) on preferred options and potential involvement.
- Attend one of five open webinars. The webinars were available for anyone to join, each with the same agenda of discussion of [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#), to engage multiple time zones.

- Comment directly on [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#).
- Email questions or comments to ReSA.

ReSA received responses from all the above modes, totalling 77 responses. Among these, 37 people completed the survey, 25 attended open webinars, 8 commented on [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#), 6 engaged via both the webinars and through comments on the paper, and 1 person sent an email to ReSA with feedback. ReSA also conducted conversations with the UK Society of Research Software Engineering (SocRSE) and the Research Data Alliance (RDA), who had not engaged in earlier consultations.

Finally, [Towards an international research software conference \(version 3\)](#) was created for participants in the previous rounds to comment on in Dec 2024 - mid-January 2025. Four people provided minor feedback for this, which was incorporated into this final version.

3. Conference options

ReSA presented three options for community consideration in [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#). These built on earlier discussions around possible aims and outcomes, stakeholder focus, and mode of engagement. All three options share a common overarching aim of community building, but differ in the communities they focus on, as shown in the following table.

	Working title	Mode	Community building focus	Outcome	Community focus
A	International Research Software Community Conference (In RSC Con)	Hybrid annual conference	Engage key stakeholders within research software community	Improve collaboration and coordination	Internal - with existing research software community
B	Events About Research Software (EARS)	Sessions / workshops at multiple existing events	Engage with overlapping/new communities	Improve valuing of research software	External - to grow the research software community
C	Champions of Research Software (ChampRS)	In-person small event	Support emerging research software champions	Enlarge pool of leaders across research community	Mostly internal but the ability to include some external

The differing community focus of the three different options was seen as particularly important, with these aims varying from primarily deepening engagement with existing stakeholders (option

A), to broadening stakeholder engagement to overlapping/new communities (option B), to supporting future community leaders (option C). However, it should be noted that there is a small overlap in community focus between option A and B, i.e., each could also engage some of the communities that the other would, albeit to a lesser extent.

These options were confirmed in the community consultation as not being addressed by existing events. These goals may currently be achieved at national and disciplinary levels in some cases, but not at a global and domain-inclusive level. Consequently, international level strategies and activities may not occur, and there are currently both silos and duplication of effort. However, given that there are already other events in which the community engages, any new event/s must provide clearly stated added value. For more details on each option, see [Towards an international research software conference \(version 2\)](#).

4. Community consultation feedback

Significant support was seen for all three options, and a number of recurring points could be seen in the community consultation: the need for more research software community building to engage members across a range of mechanisms and the need to enable engagement with underrepresented regions when planning international events.

4.1 Preferred options

To gain an understanding of which option(s) might be most useful, ReSA invited survey respondents to indicate which of the three event options listed in the options paper would be most valuable to the research software community. More than one option could be selected. As shown in the following table, 29 participants selected option A (conference) as the most valuable; 25 selected option B (workshops at existing events); and 12 selected option C (champions event).

Webinar participants also expressed support for all three options, with some preference for option A (conference), noting that the research software community is ready for, and could

benefit from, a large international event. They also highlighted the potential value of options B (sessions/workshops at existing events) and C (champions program) in community-building.

4.2 Relevant considerations

A number of issues were considered relevant to any type of event, including all of the above options. These issues are summarised below, and include diversity, equity and inclusion; environmental sustainability; and ongoing engagement.

- There is a need to consider existing and potential intersections. Should the event aim to prioritise gaps in relationships with other sectors, or strengthen intersections that already exist? Do any of the options reach the decision-makers well enough?
- There is an interest in approaching the event via two directions: bottom up (option C - champions event) and top-down (option A - conference), so that both exist in the system.
- Research software warrants its own conference, and it is also important to create opportunities for different communities (e.g., national or theme-specific) to come together in a mini-workshop, for example. It would be prudent to also include research software as a side event at larger conferences to interface with data professionals (e.g., International Data Week).
- It is important to leverage the knowledge and experience of existing organisations and initiatives.
- There must be consideration of how to promote equal access for participation in any event, particularly in terms of access to resources, caretaking responsibilities, etc. It is important to host conferences outside of the Global North at times to ensure the event is truly international and address factors (e.g., cost, visas) that may impede participation for Global South attendees. The cost of attending a conference in the Global North for participants in the Global South is very substantial (sometimes 1/5 to 1/3 of a small or medium grant), all while having to deal with much less funding being available in the first place. Travel grants can help increase diversity, but often the funding is not sufficient. For online participants, organisers must consider issues related to internet access (e.g., reach, electricity supply).
- The value of in-person interactions at conferences is recognised, although the resulting environmental impact must also be considered.
- Whilst engagement with a single, annual event has value, ongoing engagement throughout the year is needed to better achieve the goal of community building.
- Event organisers are unlikely to receive recognition for their work in a manner that could support career development. One way to assist with this is to give organisers titles such as Head or Director.

Other recurring feedback relevant to specific options is summarised here:

Option A: Conference

- There is a need to determine what a hybrid annual conference would entail (e.g., keynotes, papers, submitted talks, working sessions, tutorials) to help better understand who and how many people would attend.
- A large conference would be a big catalyst to boost local efforts and strengthen all RSE communities, including emerging ones. Starting with smaller events would not generate the same momentum, and would therefore be less impactful
- This conference is intended to differ from [RSECon](#), which is a highly successful event that has been organised by the Society of RSE in the UK for many years. The majority of RSECon's audience is RSEs, the focus is on research software engineering, and the event enables interaction between RSEs and with other key stakeholders. The proposed new event aims to engage change-makers, leaders and decision-makers from a range of stakeholder groups within the research software community, with equal representation of policy makers, national/international RSE associations, infrastructure providers, funders, university consortia, thematic communities (e.g. training), publishers, researchers on research software, etc., and with a wider focus on research software writ large, not just on its development and maintenance
- Similarly, RSECon includes RSE Worldwide sessions where all national RSE associations give updates. The proposed new event is intended to differ significantly from RSE Worldwide as it will engage many stakeholders other than RSE national associations and RSEs.
- An international research software event could fill in a few gaps by doing something different from what the current regional events do by addressing broader issues at a global level (which local events are usually not able to fully address) and convening an international event in regions that do not have strong local research software communities.
- Large international conferences typically attract people who are already invested in the community. Is this the target audience? Or do the other options offer an opportunity to engage with stakeholders in other regions?
- What might be the impact of this on other existing events, such as potentially reducing their attendance and/or funding/income? How could this also affect attendance at this event? Some stakeholders may only be able to join one event each year.
- Organising a large event can take very significant resourcing and coordination, and volunteer burnout can be a factor. Hybrid events can require organising three separate groups: in person, online, and hybrid.
- A new international conference could be partially piloted in 2025 by augmenting existing events, such as enabling workshops or co-located events at national annual RSE association events to increase engagement with other stakeholders (e.g., funders, infrastructure providers, publishers, policy makers, etc.), e.g.: the meetings of the UK ([September 2025](#)), US ([October 2025](#)), and Germany ([February 2025](#)) associations/societies.
- Hosting an event in a geographic region with high recognition of the value of research software and/or a very established RSE community (e.g., UK, USA) may not be ideal. But neither would be hosting the event in a location without this recognition, and/or an existing (emerging or established) community. Choosing a location where there is an

emerging local community around some aspect of research software, and closely working with the local community to plan and realise the event could be a more promising option.

- This could consider the whole research community and encourage other stakeholders to join the conversation about research software, and to recognise roles such as RSEs, data stewards, and research technical professionals.

Option B: Workshops at existing events

- There is a need to determine the process for prioritising and selecting which communities or groups to target for this option. For example, is the focus on enabling side events at overlapping areas where there is some interest in research software, or to focus on new areas? Would events only be funded for one year, or for a small number of subsequent years until a community had evolved that could sustain the events?
- Other issues to decide include whether workshops would always be bespoke (to fit with local communities), or could a replicable format be provided (as for the [Research Bazaar](#) (ResBaz) that has been running in Australia and New Zealand for about a decade). What kind of workshop would be admissible, and could a physical presence at a booth be supported (as can be a quite successful method for engaging many participants)?
- Branding or similar would need to be created to enable workshops co-located at other events to be seen as part of a bigger program, which includes a conference in 2026.
- The regional focus associated with this option could offer a good balance between local and global interactions and provide stakeholders in the same region with an opportunity to discuss research software challenges that may be similar within their communities.
- Smaller, more focused events with mainly active RSEs involved can be quite productive (e.g., a workshop attached to a more general software conference).
- This option offers more of an opportunity to connect with the user base and add value.
- 2025 events would need to be identified quickly, and could encompass workshops already being planned (e.g. [EVERSE](#) and [Science For Africa Foundation](#) are considering a research software quality workshop for co-location at a pan-African conference in late 2025).

Option C: Champions event

- This could be incorporated into an annual conference as a short pre/post-event. Both internal and external engagements are needed to improve the recognition of research software as a critical link in the research process.
- The focus could be on supporting champions to build communities, or how to function as change-makers within their local context.
- There needs to be consideration of how champions will be selected. Is the aim to engage already emerging leaders, or support development of new leaders in areas where champions do not exist? Some approaches may over-privilege those already

privileged – stronger leaders may come up organically; however, it could also help people who champion rather than existing leaders, and support them in their roles.

- Making it somewhat competitive can also make it more prestigious.
- Previous year's champions being involved in the following year's conference (or events), to enable both the champions and the conference some planning continuity.
- Champions can only champion if they are supported over a longer time and have access to other resources (e.g. support in their environment, funding to travel, invitation to co-author publications to help them grow their credibility). A champions program that functioned beyond attendance at a single event would be more useful.
- It would be valuable to intersect with existing fellows and champions programs, such as those of the Software Sustainability Institute, Open Life Sciences and rOpenSci. These groups are already skilled at supporting champions on their leadership journey over a year or more.
- The champions event could possibly be developed in a way so that an in-person element was not needed.

5. Community consultation analysis

This section analyses the community consultation feedback to identify option/s to progress, potential organisers and resourcing, and potential pilots.

5.1 Option/s to progress

The community consultation resulted in a lot of discussion on the value of developing a model that combines all three conference options as they achieve different outcomes and engage different communities. However, this is quite ambitious, and a valuable suggestion was to **take a sequential approach** and/or consider combining options.

For example, a sequential could begin with option B (workshops at existing events) - creating localised events that empower and strengthen local communities by bringing research software talks to existing events. This could create the momentum that would enable expansion of the potential audience to then develop the dedicated event of option A (which needs significant logistical support). Option A (conference) could include option C (champions event) via a dedicated conference track or workshop. This is illustrated in the following figure:

5.2 Potential organisers and resourcing

The survey also asked participants if they were interested in being involved in organising any of the events, with **26 unique participants** responding that they would. More than half of these 26 participants were from North America, Europe or the UK, with other regions represented by 2-3 participants each including Africa, Australia/New Zealand, and Latin America. This breakdown of their interest is shown in the following table, noting that participants could choose more than one option, which 23 respondents did (9 of which chose all three options).

13 participants also answered a survey question regarding whether their organisation would be interested in assisting with resourcing (staff time, facilities, funds, etc.) for any of the options, and specifying what they could possibly contribute. The **organisations offering potential support were varied**: universities from five continents, a national RSE association, a fiscal sponsor, and a not-for-profit organisation; and their support included:

- Staff time: 9 organisations (two of which offered dedicated events planning teams)
- Conference venues: 3 organisations
- Funding/sponsorship: 3 organisations
- Outreach and public relations: 2 organisations

With regard to funding and sponsorship, it should be noted that the community consultations did not specifically seek to engage potential funders or industry sponsors. However, [Towards an international research software conference \(version 1\)](#) had identified a range of business models utilised successfully by existing events, which **strongly suggests that a new event could be appropriately resourced** (although it is still mostly the norm that depends on volunteer effort).

Whilst some resourcing models include significant sponsorship, [Towards an international research software conference \(version 1\)](#) concluded that there is also significant evidence that cost-recovery is possible, with a range of events with varied registration costs, and/or that do receive sponsorship, from organisations such as:

- Funders/government: Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), US National Science Foundation (NSF) (mostly interested in supporting attendance of students, early career researchers, and/or members of underrepresented groups, all from the US), US Department of Energy (DOE), Wellcome Trust
- Industry/infrastructure providers: Amazon Web Services (AWS), Australian Access Federation (AAF), ByteDance, CloudKubed, Crossref, DataCite, Dreaming Spires, Dryad, Figshare (Digital Science), Ford, GitHub Education, Google, Huawei, IBM, Oracle for Research, PeerJ, Uber
- Other: Alan Turing Institute, Association of Computing Machinery (ACM), CSIRO, IEEE, IEEE Computer Society, Health Data Research UK (HDR UK), HPC Sig, SigSoft, Software Sustainability Institute (SSI), UK Met Office, Sloan Foundation

ReSA is willing to function as the lead organisation for these new events, though would need support to convene committees and do the groundwork to secure funding for these events. The community consultation invited existing events and organisations to consider if they would like to scale up or convene a new event (primarily relevant for option A), and whilst a number indicated interest in being involved, none proposed themselves for leadership.

5.3 Potential pilots

Given the above feedback that a sequential approach to convening all three event options might be a useful way to proceed, starting with option B, ideally in 2025. Earlier stages of the community consultation had identified events already planned for 2025, which could now be considered as options where option B events could be co-located, such as:

- International events in open science or other types of digital research infrastructure, e.g.:
 - The Research Data Alliance Plenary occurring at [International Data Week](#) in October 2025 in Australia.
 - The EOSC Association [Open Science Conference](#) in Germany in October 2025.

- National Research and Education Network (NREN) meeting such as [UbuntuNet Connect](#) in Africa in late 2025, or Asia Pacific Advanced Networks (APAN) [meeting](#) in Hong Kong in July.
- Disciplinary events, e.g.:
 - European Geosciences Union (EGU) [General Assembly](#) in Vienna in April 2025.
- Events focused on open source science, e.g.:
 - JupyterCon in California in November 2025.

However, organising needs to commence quickly to enable this, to fit with future event planning timelines, enable shared branding and potentially provide financial support.

6. Recommendations

The benefits of this activity to the community have been to systematically investigate this issue, as the potential benefits of a regular, international research software event are often identified by the community; however, the coordinating body (and business model) for doing so has been unclear. ReSA's role in collaborating across the community (as per [ReSA's mission](#) to advance the research software ecosystem by collaborating with decision makers and key influencers) has provided the mandate needed to lead the community discussions needed to identify a solution that the community will support.

More than this, this consultation has enabled the community to identify its needs in terms of community development, which extend beyond annual events to ongoing opportunities throughout the year, and a champions program. This has resulted in the following recommendations:

1. Proceed with the sequential approach, with option B (workshops at existing events) occurring in 2025, to learn from this experience and evaluate outcomes, and to build momentum towards all options taking place in 2026.
2. Form committees led by ReSA to begin development of all three options in early 2025, including identifying resourcing.
 - d. Option B (workshops at existing events) is the priority, to enable 2025 events to occur.
 - e. Option A (conference) will need at least 12 months of forward planning so this also needs to commence in 2025. Invite the Society of RSE to join this committee to consider the relationship with RSECon.
 - f. Option C (champions event) would benefit from formation in 2025 to provide lead time to consider development of a champions program, rather than a single, annual champions event.
3. Ensure that the event planning from the start includes principles to support both diversity, equity and inclusion, and environmental sustainability.

- a. Utilise the experience of both committee members and ReSA (e.g. in co-leading international events such as the Lorentz Centre workshop: [Vive la différence – research software engineers](#) where DEI was central to both the workshop content and its design).

7. Acknowledgements

ReSA gratefully acknowledges the inputs of many community members into the development of the options and recommendations contained in this report. Without them, this work would not have been possible.

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